



(a) Scenario T1



(b) Scenario T3



(c) Scenario T5

Figure 4: The confidence score distributions for Scenarios T1, T3, and T5 in the Ask Ubuntu dataset.



(a) Scenario T1



(b) Scenario T3

Figure 5: The confidence score distributions for Scenarios T1, T3, and T5 in the Stack Overflow dataset.